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Five new Tettigoniidae species (Orthoptera) from Balkan Peninsula

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SUMMARY. During several entomological excursions in Montenegro and East Hercegovina between 1997 and 2010 five new species of Orthoptera (Tettigoniidae) were discovered: *Poecilimon perovici* sp. n. (Montenegro), *Poecilimon lasicai* sp. n. (Montenegro) and *Poecilimon mehmedbegovici* sp. n. (Montenegro) from the subfamily Phaneropterinae, *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n. (Montenegro) and *Pholidoptera antonijevici* sp. n. (East Hercegovina) from the subfamily Tettigoniinae. The morphological characters of the new species are analyzed and data on their ecological preferences reported.

KEY WORDS: East Hercegovina, Montenegro, Phaneropterinae, *Pholidoptera*, *Poecilimon*, Tettigoniinae.

INTRODUCTION

Orthoptera are one of the most diverse insect group with over 27500 species described so far (Cigliano et al. 2017). In the recent years we became witnesses of a geometric progression in discovery of new orthopteran taxa, especially in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. The Orthoptera fauna of Europe is most highly studied with 1108 species known so far (Hochkirch et al. 2016). The greatest diversity has been recorded from the Mediterranean area and the Balkan Peninsula. The largest numbers of endemic species are present on the Iberian, Apennine and Balkan Peninsulas, as well as from some high mountain areas such as the Alps, Pyrenees, Carpathians and Apennines (Hochkirch et al. 2016). The Balkan Peninsula accommodating 40% of the European bush cricket fauna, represents a hot spot of their biodiversity. More than 290 Orthoptera species are endemic to the Balkan Peninsula. Despite that the Orthoptera fauna of this region is relatively well studied, there are still some vast areas waiting to become thoroughly investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Voucher specimens have been collected manually, then dry pinned. Photographs of stridulatory files of males have been taken on an electronic microscope (JEOL JSM 6460 LV) at the University Centre for Electron Microscopy – Novi Sad and partly in Natural History Museum Vienna with JEOL JSM 6610-LV at an accelerating voltage of 15kV. Before scanning samples were mounted on aluminum stubs equipped with a sticky aluminum tape coated with platinum (Leica EM-SCD500). Systematics is based on Ramme (1951), Harz (1969) and Ingrisch and Pavićević (2010).

ABBREVIATIONS

CDPV- Private Collection of Dragan Pavićević, Belgrade, Serbia.

SYSTEMATIC PART**Orthoptera****Tettigoniidae****Phaneropterinae**

The genus *Poecilimon* Fischer, 1853 is one the richest Palearctic orthopteran genera, consisting of almost 182 valid taxa – 142 species and 40 subspecies (Cigliano et al. 2020). It is distributed from the Apennines to Western Siberia and Central Tien – Shan (Bey –Bienko 1954).

***Poecilimon elegans* group**

This group consist of two species, *Poecilimon elegans* Brunner, 1878 and *Poecilimon albolineatus* Ingrisch & Pavićević, 2010 (Ingrisch and Pavićević 2010) so far. In the same article the authors mentioned some specimens which show some morphological differences from both described species, one of them was from the costal part of Croatia as well as from Metković and Korčula Island, the second one was from Montenegro (Mt. Lovćen) and East Hercegovina (Mt. Orjen). Unfortunately I didn't have the possibility to examine those specimens that are depositet at the Museum Koenig in Bonn, instead I studied specimens from my own collection.

***Poecilimon perovici* sp. n. (Figs 1, 2, 3A)**

HOLOTYPE (MALE): Montenegro: Nikšić, Donje Čaradje, Ćurilo, 1100 m asl, 2 July 2010, leg. D. Pavićević (CDPV). PARATYPES: 1 male, 4 females, same data as holotype (CDPV).

DIAGNOSIS. In general appearance, size and coloration, *P. perovici* sp. n. is very similar to *P. albolineatus*. It differs from it by the shape of the stridulatory file as well as by the shape of the male subgenital plate.

DESCRIPTION. A medium-sized species with males measuring 22–23 mm, females 20–24 mm.

MALE (Figs 1A, 2A–C, 3A). Scapus 1.2–2.0 times wider than fastigium verticis. Fastigium verticis dorsally furrowed. Pronotum (Fig. 2A) saddle like, 4.5–5.0 mm long, constricted near middle of length in the transverse sulcus area, with posterior area slightly raised; apex shallowly concave. Micropterous, tegmina

Fig. 1. *Poecilimon perovici* sp. n. A, male holotype; B, female, paratype.

Fig. 2. *Poecilimon perovici* sp. n., male holotype (A–C) and female paratype (D–F). **A**, pronotum and tegmina, dorsal view; **B**, abdominal apex with cerci, dorsal view; **C**, subgenital plate, ventral view; **D**, pronotum, dorsal view; **E**, subgenital plate, ventral view; **F**, ovipositor. Scale bars 1 mm.

Fig. 3. SEM Photos of tegmina with stridulatory files. **A**, *Poccilimon perovici* sp. n., holotype; **B**, *Poccilimon albolineatus* Ingrisch and Pavićević, 2010.

1.4–1.5 mm; Stridulatory file (3A) almost straight, with 89–94 teeth. Cerci (Fig. 2B) strongly curved, slightly flattened before apex narrowing into apical median tooth. Subgenital plate (Fig. 2C) narrowing before apex, incised in middle. Postfemur 14.5–16 mm.

FEMALE (Figs 1B, 2D–F). Scapus 1.2–1.5 times wider than fastigium verticis. Fastigium verticis dorsally furrowed. Pronotum (Fig. 2D) 4–4.5 mm, slightly widening posteriorly, flattened, apex almost straight. Squamipterous, tegmina completely hidden. Cerci conical. Subgenital plate (Fig. 2E) transverse triangular. Ovipositor (Fig. 2F) 8–8.5 mm, sabre shaped, weakly raised, apical third dentate. Postfemur 16–17 mm.

COLORATION. Almost of same coloration as *P. albolineatus*. Male: green with black speckles (Fig. 1A). Pronotum with narrow white median line and with white lateral stripes, inside them, from both sides bordered with interrupted reddish narrow stripes. Paranota with a narrow white band along ventral margin. Tegmina yellowish with a dark brown spot at hind margin. Abdominal tergites green with white lateral bands bordered externally by a black line and with a median black band, interrupted by a white line.

Female: Green with black or dark brown speckles (Fig. 1B). Pronotum same as in male. Abdominal tergites with a median and two lateral white bands, the lateral stripe bordered externally by a narrow dark brown line; median band white colored.

ETYMOLOGY. The new species is named after Drago Perović, professor of Philosophy at Faculty of Philosophy in Nikšić in recognition of his generous help in organizing the expedition on Golija Mt. (Montenegro) in July 2010.

HABITAT AND DISTRIBUTION. Mesophilic clearing overgrown with dense *Rubus* shrubs. Known only from the type locality, village Donje Čaradje in north western part of Montenegro (Fig. 15).

COMMENT. *Poecilimon perovici* sp. n. differs from the closely related *P. albolineatus* by a curved stridulatory file (Fig. 3A) which is in *P. albolineatus* almost straight (Fig. 3B); by the subgenital plate which has the apical part longer, strongly narrowing and with subparallel margins (Fig. 2C) while in *P. albolineatus* the subgenital plate apical part is short and slightly narrowing. The male subgenital plate of the of the new species is intermediate between those in *P. albolineatus* and *P. elegans*. In females of *P. perovici* sp. n. the subgenital plate (Fig. 2E) is wider than in *P. albolineatus*. The new species is known only from the locus typicus. The close related species *P. albolineatus* is present in the nearby localities, Krstac, Javljen, Stozi and Jasikovica. *Poecilimon. albolineatus* was described from Mt. Durmitor (Montenegro) but is obviously widely present in the region. In East Hercegovina I found it in Njemenice (Mt. Baba), Brestice – Korita (Bileća) and Dabarsko polje near Berkovići (Fig. 15) (unpublished data).

Poecilimon lasicai sp. n. (Figs 4-6A)

HOLOTYPE (MALE): Montenegro, Mt. Orjen, Krivošije, Knežlaz, 600 m asl, 8 July 1997, leg. D. Pavićević (CDPV). PARTYPES: 1 male, same data as holotype (CDPV).

DIAGNOSIS. The new species is closely related to *P. albolineatus* and *P. perovici* sp. n. It differs from both by the stridulatory file and the shape of the subgenital plate.

The female is unknown.

DESCRIPTION. A medium size species, measuring 22 mm.

MALE (Figs 4A, 5, 6A). Scapus 1.2 times as broad as fastigium verticis. Fastigium verticis dorsally furrowed. Pronotum (Fig. 5A) saddle shaped, 4.5 mm long, constricted close to middle length of transverse sulcus area, posterior area slightly raised; apex shallowly concave. Micropterous, tegmina 1.5 mm; stridulatory file (Fig. 6A) slightly curved with about 130 teeth. Cerci (Fig. 5B) strongly curved, slightly flattened before apex narrowing into apical median tooth. Subgenital plate (Fig. 5C) relatively broad, narrowing just before apex, shallowly incised in middle. Postfemur 16 mm.

COLORATION. Yellowish light green with rare dark brown dots (Fig. 4A). Pronotum with narrow white median line and with wide white lateral stripes. Paranota with a narrow white band along the ventral margin. Tegmina yellowish with a dark brown spot at hind margin. Abdominal tergites yellowish green with wide white lateral bands bordered externally by a narrow black line and with a wide median black band.

ETIMOLOGY. *Poecilimon lasicai* sp. n. is dedicated to doc. Prof. Dr. Ratko M. Lasic, Coronary Care Unit, Clinical Centre of Serbia, Emergency Hospital, Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia.

Fig. 4. Habitus photos. A. *Poecilimon lasicai* sp. n. male, holotype; B, *Poecilimon mehmedbegovici* sp. n. male, holotype.

Fig. 5. *Poecilimon lasicai* sp. n., holotype male. **A**, pronotum and tegmina, dorsal view; **B**, abdominal apex with cerci, dorsal view; **C**, subgenital plate, ventral view. Scale bars 1 mm.

Fig. 6. SEM photos of tegmina with stridulatory files. **A**, *Poecilimon lasicai* sp. n., holotype; **B**, *Poecilimon mehmedbegovici* sp. n., holotype.

HABITAT AND DISTRIBUTION. Clearings in sparse oak forest with *Salvia* bushes at 600 m asl. Known only from the type locality (Fig. 15).

COMMENT. *Poecilimon lasicai* sp. n. is closely related to *P. perovici* sp. n. and *P. albolinetus*. It differs distinctly from both species by the slightly curved stridulation file with almost 130 teeth and by the different shape of subgenital plate. In *P. perovici* sp. n. the stridulatory file is strongly curved, with 89–94 teeth, while in *P. albolineatus* it is almost straight and with 95–96 teeth.

Poecilimon mehmedbegovici sp. n. (Figs 4B, 6B, 7)

HOLOTYPE (MALE): Montenegro, Ulcinj, Velika plaža, 5 July 2003, leg. D. Pavićević (CDPV). PARATYPES: 1 male, same data as holotype (CDPV).

DIAGNOSIS. The new species is closely related to *Poecilimon albolineatus*. It differs from it through different shape of stridulatory file and subgenital plate.

The female is unknown.

DESCRIPTION. A medium sized species, males measuring 20–21 mm.

MALE. Scapus 1.6–1.9 times as broad as fastigium verticis. Fastigium verticis shallowly to deeply furrowed above. Pronotum (Fig. 7A) 4.4–4.5 mm, saddle like, constricted near mid length in the transverse sulcus area, with posterior area slightly raised; apex shallowly concave. Micropterous, tegmina 1.4–1.5 mm. Stridulatory file (Fig. 6B) weakly curved with about 96–100 teeth. Cerci (Fig. 7B) strongly curved, slightly flattened before apex narrowing into apical median tooth. Subgenital plate (Fig. 7C) narrowing before apex, incised in middle. Postfemur length 16 mm.

COLORATION. Yellowish green with random dark brown dots (Fig. 4B). Male: Pronotum with narrow white median line broken in sulcus area and with white lateral stripes, inside them, from both sides bordered with interrupted reddish narrow stripe. Paranota with a narrow white band along ventral margin. Tegmina yellowish with a dark brown spot at hind margin. Abdominal tergites yellowish green with white lateral bands bordered externally by a black line and with a median black band, interrupted by a white line.

ETYMOLOGY. *Poecilimon mehmedbegovici* sp. n. is dedicated to Prof. Dr. Zlatko Mehmedbegović, Emergency Department Clinic for Cardiology, Clinical Center of Serbia, Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Serbia.

HABITAT AND DISTRIBUTION. Velika plaža costal dunes with sparse and low vegetation. Known only from type locality (Fig. 15). In same habitat the new species appears sympatrically with a population of numerous *Poecilimon jonicus* (Fischer, 1853).

COMMENT. The stridulation file in *P. mehmedbegovici* is less curved than in *P. perovici* sp. n. but stronger than in *P. lasicai* sp. n. The subgenital plate of the

Fig. 7. *Poecilimon mehmedbegovici* sp. n., male holotype. **A**, pronotum and tegmina, dorsal view; **B**, abdominal apex with cerci, dorsal view; **C**, subgenital plate, ventral view. Scale bars 1 mm.

P. mehmedbegovici sp. n. is wider and with apical part more drawn up than in *P. albolineatus*, almost the same as in *P. perovici* sp. n., but wider in basal area than in the latter species.

Poecilimon perovici sp. n., *P. lasicaei* sp. n., *P. mehmedbegovici* sp. n. and *P. albolineatus* are closely related species which belong together with the nominal species to the *Poecilimon elegans* group of species. All mentioned species are missing two distinct steps on the stridulatory file which are characteristic for *P. elegans* (Ingrisch and Pavićević 2010, fig. 15B).

Tettigoniinae

Among the 14 taxa of *Pholidoptera* Wesmael, 1838 presented in the European fauna some of them are widely distributed, such as *Pholidoptera fallax* (Fischer, 1853). The area comprehends large part of the Balkan Peninsula, Italy, Sardinia and Sicilia, reaching Slovakia in the north and southeastern France in the west,

while the easternmost border of its distribution is Moldavia (Hochkirch 2016). The German orthopterologist, Willy Ramme (1951) wrote in his book: "...bei *fallax* males besteht individuell, und im Süden fast subspezifisch die Neigung zu etwas stärkerer Entwicklung der Elytren, dennoch ist die Art in Habitus, Färbung, Zeichnung und Bau des Epiphallus eng mit *femorata* verbunden." Ramme called them "Doppelarten" (today perhaps something like sibling species) because of their great similarity. Almost the same wrote Heller (1988): "*Die beiden Arten Ph. femorata* und *Ph. fallax* sind morphologisch („Doppelarten“ bei RAMME, 1951) und in Gesang sehr ähnlich Ihr Status sollte anhand genauerer Untersuchungen der Verbreitung weiter untersucht werden. Obwohl ihre Verbreitungsgebiete sich fast vollständig überdecken, kommen sie kaum syntop (oder sogar sympatrisch s. F. WILLEMSE 1984) vor, da sie anscheinend ganz unterschiedliche ökologische Ansprüche zeigen."

In his book Ramme didn't mention the locality(ies) in South Europe where he found *P. fallax*. which so much resemble *P. femorata* (Fieber, 1853).

In previous years I have found *P. fallax* in a lot of localities in Serbia, Bosnia & Hercegovina and Montenegro. They were collected at different altitudes, from 196 m (Beočin near Danube river – Serbia) up to 1800 m (Prokletije Mts. – Montenegro). In a spite of the great height discrepancy, the examined specimens didn't show remarkable differences in size of body and other morphological characters. In some publications on Orthoptera can be found that specimens from lowland are remarkable larger than those from higher altitudes (Chobanov and Heller 2010). For this study I have examined more than one hundred specimens of *P. fallax* from Serbia, Bosnia and Hercegovina and Montenegro, collected in different habitats and on different altitudes. As a result of the study I have found that the size of the examined *P. fallax* specimens does not correlate with altitude. Having that fact in mind, beside some obvious morphological differences, I have recognized two new species closely related to *Ph. fallax*. The first one, *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n. from Ulcinj (Gornji Štoj – Bregvija) was found at a forest clearing in syntopy with an abundant population of *Ph. femorata*. The populations from Ulcinj could belong to Ramme's "Doppelart" (or sibling species today) because of similar body size of the two species. During random field collecting, males of this new species, could be overlooked and confused with males of *P. femorata* mainly because of their size. Otherwise, there is no problem to distinguish these two species, since *Ph. femorata* is a little bigger, males have remarkable shorter elytra, different cerci and females have a much longer ovipositor. The second species, *Pholidoptera antonijevidici* sp. n. from Dramešina Gorge near Gacko (Eastern Hercegovina) at first sight strikingly resemble *P. fallax*.

Pholidoptera ruzae sp. n. (Figs 8, 9, 10A-C, 14A)

HOLOTYPE (male), Montenegro, Ulcinj, Gornji Štoj, Bregvija, 5 July 2003, leg. D. Pavićević (CDPV). PARATYPES: 3 males, 3 females, same data as holotype (CDPV).

Measurements. Body: male 24–26 mm, female 24–31 mm; pronotum: male 7.5–8 mm, female 7.5–9.5 mm; tegmen: male 3.0 mm, female 0.0 mm; hind femur: male 21–22 mm, female 21–24 mm; ovipositor 13–15 mm.

DIAGNOSIS. At first sight, the new species looks like *Pholidoptera fallax* (Fischer, 1853) but it differs by a larger and more plump body, in average longer pronotum and hind femurs in both sexes, the lower number of teeth of the stridulatory file, different cerci and titillators in males, longer and strongly curved ovipositor in females.

DESCRIPTION. Medium sized species, males measuring between 24–26 mm, females 24–31 mm.

MALE. Pronotum (Fig. 9A) slightly convex, without median carina; completely rounded into paranota. Males micropterous, length of weakly curved stridulatory file (Figs 10A–C) (diagonal): $6.408 (500 \mu\text{m}) \Rightarrow 3.204 \text{ mm}$ with 83 teeth (and a triangular field of minute extra teeth at tip) $\Rightarrow 25.91$ teeth per mm. One third of tegmina covered by pronotum. Tenth abdominal tergite (Fig. 9B) elongate, furrowed in midline; apical margin truncate in middle, weakly concave at both sides. Epiproct small; broadly rounded. Cerci (Fig. 9B) weakly curved with small inner tooth before middle, toward apex almost straight; subgenital plate (Fig. 9C) wide, obtusely excised at apex; styli thin. Tittillator (Fig. 14A) branches widely spaced, strongly curved, each branch with several spines at tip.

FEMALE. Pronotum (Fig. 9D) slightly convex without median carina completely rounded into paranota; squamipterous. Subgenital plate (Fig. 9E) rounded. Ovipositor (Fig. 9F) curved upwards.

COLORATION. Ochre, greyish-brown to dark brown (Figs 8A–B) Vertex with black spots at both sides; ventral side with two wide black post-ocular bands. Pronotum with disc brown; paranota black with broad white ventral margin. Abdominal tergites brown; abdominal sternites lemon-green to yellow.

ETYMOLOGY. *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n. is dedicated to my wife, Ruza Kovačević, in gratitude for her great support to my scientific work.

HABITAT AND DISTRIBUTION. Forest clearing with shrubs and herbaceous vegetation. Known only from the type locality (Fig. 15).

COMMENT. The new species can be easily distinguished from closely related *P. fallax* by bigger body, longer pronotum and hind femur in both sexes; more strongly curved stridulatory file with lower number of teeth (83) (stridulatory file of *P.*

Fig. 8. Habitus photos of *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n.
A, female, paratype; B, male, holotype.

Fig. 9. *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n., male holotype (A-C) and female paratype (D-F). **A**, pronotum and tegmina, dorsal view; **B**, abdominal apex with cerci, dorsal view; **C**, subgenital plate, ventral view; **D**, pronotum, dorsal view; **E**, subgenital plate, ventral view; **F**, ovipositor. Scale bars 1 mm.

Fig. 10. SEM photos of tegmina with stridulatory files. **A-C**, *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n., holotype; **D-F**, *Pholidoptera femorata* (Fieber, 1853)

fallax is almost straight with a higher number of teeth (87–95)); different titilators and cerci in males and longer and more upward curved ovipositor in females.

REMARKS. *Pholidoptera ruzae* sp. n. was found in syntopy with an abundant population of *Ph. femorata* (Figs 11A-B). The populations from Ulcinj could belong to

Fig. 11. Habitus photos of *Pholidoptera femorata* (Fieber, 1853): **A**, male; **B**, female.

Rammes „Doppelart“ (or sibling species today), as during random field collecting, males of this new species, could be easily overlooked and confused with males of *P. femorata*. Males of *P. ruzae* sp. n. highly resemble males of *P. femorata* not only in body size but also in shapes of stridulatory file and titillators. Females of both species are easily recognizable since females of *P. femorata* have very long, weakly upwards curved ovipositor (19–23 mm) while in *P. ruzae* sp. n. the ovipositor is much shorter (13–15 mm) and more strongly upwards curved.

Pholidoptera antonijevidi sp. n. (Figs 12, 13A–C, 14C)

HOLOTYPE (male), East Hercegovina: Gacko, Dramešina gorge (foothill of Lebršnik Mt.), 1200 m asl, 11 September 2006, leg. D. Pavićević (CDPV). PARATYPES: 2 males, 5 females, same data as holotype.

MEASUREMENTS. Body: male 22–22.5 mm, female 22.5–24 mm; pronotum: male 6.5 mm, female 6.5 mm; tegmen: male 3.0–3.5 mm, female, 0.0 mm; hind femur: male 16.5–20.0 mm, female 19–21 mm; ovipositor: 11.0–13 mm.

DIAGNOSIS. At first sight the new species look like *Pholidoptera fallax* (Fischer, 1853) but it differs from it by larger body, longer hind femora in both sexes, different shape of stridulation file and by the ovipositor being more strongly curved upwards.

DESCRIPTION. Medium sized species.

MALE. Pronotum (Fig. 12A) slightly convex, without median carina; completely rounded into paranota. Males micropterous, stridulatory file weakly curved (Figs 13A–F) with 96 teeth (and a small cluster of minute extra teeth at tip). The second half of elytra with short rhomboid teeth. One third of tegmina covered by pronotum. Tenth abdominal tergite (Fig. 12B) elongate, weakly furrowed in midline; apical margin truncate in middle, weakly concave at both sides. Epiproct small; triangular, obtuse. Cerci (Fig. 12B) completely straight or weakly curved in basal area; with a small inner tooth in basal third or before the middle. Subgenital plate (Fig. 12C) wide, obtusely excised in middle. Titillator (Fig. 14C) branches widely spaced, strongly curved, with two strong spines at apex.

FEMALE. Pronotum (Fig. 12D) slightly convex without median carina, completely rounded into paranota. Tegmen squamipterous. Subgenital plate as in Fig. 12E. Ovipositor (Fig. 12F) strongly curved upwards.

COLORATION. Ochre, greyish-brown to dark brown. Vertex with black spots at both sides; ventral side with two wide black post-ocular bands. Pronotum with disc brown; paranota black with broad white ventral margin. Abdominal tergites brown; sternites lemon-green to yellow.

ETYMOLOGY. *Pholidoptera antonijevidi* sp. n. is dedicated to. Prof. Dr. Nebojša Antonijević, Clinic for Cardiology, University Clinical Center of Serbia, Faculty of

Fig. 12. *Pholidoptera antonijevis* sp. n., male holotype (A-C), female paratype (D-F). **A**, pronotum and tegmina, dorsal view; **B**, abdominal apex with cerci, dorsal view; **C**, subgenital plate, ventral view; **D**, pronotum, dorsal view; **E**, subgenital plate, ventral view; **F**, ovipositor. Scale bars 1 mm.

Fig. 13. SEM photos of tegmina with stridulatory file. **A-C**, *Pholidoptera antonijevicei* sp. n., holotype; **D-F**, *Pholidoptera fallax* (Fischer, 1853).

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HABITAT AND DISTRIBUTION. East Hercegovina, Gacko, Dramešina gorge, 1200 m asl (Fig. 15), natural rock terraces with semi dried herbaceous vegetation on abrupt sides of the gorge. The gorge is mostly overgrown with impenetrable dense forest

Figure 14. Titillators. **A**, *Poecilimon ruzae* sp. n., holotype; **B**, *Pholidoptera femorata* (Fieber, 1853); **C**, *Pholidoptera antonijevicei* sp. n., holotype; **D-F**, *Pholidoptera fallax* (Fischer, 1853). Scale bar 1 mm.

(mostly *Carpinus* and *Corylus*). Known only from the type locality. In the same habitat the new species appears simpatrically with *Pholidoptera griseoaptera* (De Geer, 1773).

COMMENT. The new species differs from the closely related *P. fallax* (Figs 13D–F, 14D–F) by larger body and longer hind legs in both sexes, by a different shape of the stridulatory file, male cerci, as well as by longer and more upwards curved ovopositor. The middle part of the stridulatory file of *P. antonijevicei* sp. n. is curved (Fig. 13A) while in *P. fallax* it is almost straight (Fig. 13D). The number of teeth on the stridulatory file in *P. antonijevicei* sp. n. is around 96 while in *P. fallax* it is between 87–95. The most striking difference is the shape of the teeth of the stridulatory file. In *P. antonijevicei* the teeth of the second half of the file are short and of rhomboidal shape (Fig. 13C) while in *P. fallax* they are longer and of oval elongated shape (Fig. 13F). The apex of the titillator branches (Fig. 14D–F) can vary in *P. fallax* while in *P. antonijevicei* it is very steady.

Fig. 15. Species distribution. AL - Albania; BH - Bosnia and Herzegovina; MN - Montenegro; SRB - Serbia.

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